

Online Supplementary Materials

Disparities and Factors Associated with Coronavirus Disease-2019-Related Public Stigma: A Cross-Sectional Study in Thailand

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Supplementary Online Content

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Table S1 Participants Characteristics According to the Degree of COVID-19-Related Public Stigma in Thailand

Characteristics	Overall (n=4,004)	COVID-19-related public stigma			P Value
		No/minimal: COVID-PSS ≤18 points (n=983)	Moderate: COVID-PSS 19 – 25 points (n=1,364)	High: COVID-PSS ≥26 points (n=1,657)	
COVID-PSS, mean (SD); range	24.2 (7.6); 10–50	14.9 (2.6); 10–18	21.9 (2.0); 19–25	31.6 (4.8); 26–50	<0.001
Age, year, mean (SD); range	29.1 (10.8); 18–79	27.6 (9.0); 18–65	27.9 (9.7); 18–79	30.8 (12.3); 18–73	<0.001
≤30	2,659 (66.4)	704 (71.6)	953 (69.9)	1,002 (60.5)	<0.001
31–50	1,088 (27.2)	253 (25.8)	355 (26.0)	480 (29.0)	
≥51	257 (6.4)	26 (2.6)	56 (4.1)	175 (10.6)	
Sexual identity					
Female	2,619 (65.4)	673 (68.5)	896 (65.7)	1,050 (63.4)	0.001
Male	1,231 (30.7)	260 (26.4)	415 (30.4)	556 (33.5)	
Others	154 (3.9)	50 (5.1)	53 (3.9)	51 (3.1)	
Marital status					
Single	3,208 (80.1)	854 (86.9)	1,162 (85.2)	1,192 (71.9)	<0.001
Married/domestic partnership	693 (17.3)	115 (11.7)	170 (12.5)	408 (24.6)	
Divorced/widowed/ separated	103 (2.6)	14 (1.4)	32 (2.3)	57 (3.4)	
Education level					
Illiterate/primary school/ junior high school	127 (3.2)	28 (2.8)	41 (3.0)	58 (3.5)	0.459
Senior high school/diploma/ high vocational	1,893 (47.3)	482 (49.0)	654 (48.0)	757 (45.7)	
Bachelor’s degree/ higher education	1,984 (49.5)	473 (48.1)	669 (49.0)	842 (50.8)	
Occupation					
Unemployed/retried	391 (9.8)	95 (7.7)	129 (9.5)	167 (10.1)	0.035
Employed	2,024 (50.5)	480 (48.8)	663 (48.6)	881 (53.2)	
College student	1,589 (39.7)	408 (41.5)	572 (41.9)	609 (36.7)	
Religion					
Irreligion	375 (9.4)	143 (14.6)	126 (9.2)	106 (6.4)	<0.001
Buddhist	3,454 (86.3)	787 (80.1)	1,183 (86.7)	1,484 (89.6)	
Christian/Muslim/Others	175 (4.4)	53 (5.4)	55 (4.0)	67 (4.0)	

Data are expressed as the frequency (percentage) of patients, unless otherwise indicated.

Abbreviations: COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale; SD, standard deviation.

Table S1 Participants Characteristics According to the Degree of COVID-19-Related Public Stigma in Thailand (Continued)

Characteristics	Overall (n=4,004)	COVID-19-related public stigma			P Value
		No/minimal: COVID-PSS ≤18 points (n=983)	Moderate: COVID-PSS 19 – 25 points (n=1,364)	High: COVID-PSS ≥26 points (n=1,657)	
Region of residence					
Capital city and its environs	1,425 (35.6)	412 (41.9)	498 (36.5)	515 (31.1)	<0.001
Non-capital city and its environs	2,579 (64.4)	571 (58.1)	866 (63.5)	1,142 (68.9)	
Living status					
Alone	576 (14.4)	161 (16.4)	203 (14.9)	212 (12.8)	0.023
With family	3,164 (79.0)	745 (75.8)	1,074 (78.7)	1,345 (81.2)	
With others	264 (6.6)	77 (7.8)	87 (6.4)	100 (6.0)	
Person income, baht/month					
≤10,000	1,905 (47.6)	465 (47.3)	654 (47.9)	786 (47.4)	0.001
10,001–20,000	1,054 (26.3)	299 (30.4)	357 (26.2)	398 (24.0)	
>20,000	1,045 (26.1)	219 (22.3)	353 (25.9)	473 (28.6)	
Reimbursement scheme					
Government/state enterprises	539 (13.5)	112 (11.4)	157 (11.5)	270 (16.3)	0.002
Universal coverage scheme	1,329 (33.2)	346 (35.2)	466 (34.2)	517 (31.2)	
Social security scheme	1,161 (29.0)	284 (28.9)	402 (29.5)	475 (28.7)	
Self-payment/others	975 (24.3)	241 (24.5)	339 (24.8)	395 (23.8)	
History of mental illness	359 (9.0)	108 (11.0)	115 (8.4)	136 (8.2)	0.041
History of chronic NCDs [†]	599 (15.0)	122 (12.4)	177 (13.0)	300 (18.1)	<0.001
Income loss during the COVID-19 pandemic	1,664 (41.6)	398 (40.5)	539 (39.5)	727 (43.9)	0.040
Financial problems during the COVID-19 pandemic	2,012 (50.2)	485 (49.3)	651 (47.7)	876 (52.9)	0.016

Data are expressed as the frequency (percentage) of patients, unless otherwise indicated.

[†]To includes diabetes mellitus, hypertension, dyslipidemia, stroke and heart disease, chronic kidney disease, chronic lung disease, and cancer.

Abbreviations: COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale; NCDs, non-communicable diseases.

Table S1 Participants Characteristics According to the Degree of COVID-19-Related Public Stigma in Thailand (Continued)

Characteristics	Overall (n=4,004)	COVID-19-related public stigma			P Value
		No/minimal: COVID-PSS ≤18 points (n=983)	Moderate: COVID-PSS 19 – 25 points (n=1,364)	High: COVID-PSS ≥26 points (n=1,657)	
Information exposure during the COVID-19 pandemic					
<1 hour/day	1,481 (37.0)	408 (41.5)	503 (36.9)	570 (34.4)	0.001
1–2 hours/day	1,644 (41.1)	391 (39.8)	571 (41.9)	682 (41.2)	
≥3 hours/day	879 (21.9)	184 (18.7)	290 (21.3)	405 (24.4)	
Confirmed cases in the community					
No	2,562 (64.0)	637 (64.8)	871 (63.9)	1,054 (63.6)	0.113
Yes	641 (16.0)	136 (13.8)	215 (15.8)	290 (17.5)	
Not known	801 (20.0)	210 (21.4)	278 (20.4)	313 (18.9)	
Quarantine status					
Never	1,781 (44.5)	486 (49.4)	567 (41.6)	728 (43.9)	0.004
Past	1,575 (39.3)	359 (36.5)	563 (41.3)	653 (39.4)	
Current	648 (16.2)	138 (14.1)	234 (17.1)	276 (16.7)	
Working from home	3,139 (78.4)	774 (78.7)	1,071 (78.5)	1,294 (78.1)	0.920
Multidimensional scale of perceived social support, mean (SD); range	59.1 (13.7); 12–84	58.0 (13.8); 12–84	59.7 (13.2); 12–84	59.2 (14.1); 12–84	0.016
Low perceived support	226 (5.6)	59 (6.0)	69 (5.1)	98 (5.9)	<0.001
Moderate perceived support	1,833 (45.8)	501 (51.0)	574 (42.1)	658 (45.8)	
High perceived support	1,945 (48.6)	423 (43.0)	721 (52.9)	801 (48.3)	
Brief resilient coping scale, mean (SD); range	13.9 (3.1); 4–20	13.9 (3.1); 4–20	13.8 (3.1); 4–20	13.9 (3.0); 4–20	0.416
Low resilient copers	678 (16.9)	165 (16.8)	234 (17.2)	279 (16.8)	0.967
Medium resilient copers	1,570 (39.2)	393 (40.0)	525 (38.5)	652 (39.4)	
High resilient copers	1,756 (43.9)	425 (43.2)	605 (44.3)	726 (43.8)	

Data are expressed as the frequency (percentage) of patients, unless otherwise indicated.

Abbreviations: COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale; SD, standard deviation.

Table S1 Participants Characteristics According to the Degree of COVID-19-Related Public Stigma in Thailand (Continued)

Characteristics	Overall (n=4,004)	COVID-19-related public stigma			P Value
		No/minimal: COVID-PSS ≤18 points (n=983)	Moderate: COVID-PSS 19 – 25 points (n=1,364)	High: COVID-PSS ≥26 points (n=1,657)	
Fear of COVID-19, mean (SD); range	6.6 (1.8); 1–10	5.0 (1.5); 1–9	6.3 (1.4); 2–10	7.8 (1.4); 3–10	<0.001
No/minimal	200 (5.0)	169 (17.2)	29 (2.1)	2 (0.1)	<0.001
Moderate	1,698 (42.4)	662 (67.3)	754 (55.3)	282 (17.0)	
Severe	2,106 (52.6)	152 (15.5)	581 (42.6)	1,373 (82.9)	
Perceived risk of COVID-19 infection, mean (SD); range	5.5 (2.2); 2–10	3.3 (1.2); 2–10	5.1 (1.5); 2–10	7.2 (1.6); 2–10	<0.001
Low perceived risk	767 (19.1)	584 (59.4)	171 (12.5)	12 (0.7)	<0.001
Medium perceived risk	1,997 (49.9)	385 (39.2)	990 (72.6)	622 (37.5)	
High perceived risk	1,240 (31.0)	14 (1.4)	203 (14.9)	1,023 (61.7)	

Data are expressed as the frequency (percentage) of patients, unless otherwise indicated.

Abbreviations: COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale; SD, standard deviation.

Table S2 Linear Regression Model Results of Factors Associated with COVID-19-Related Public Stigma (n=4,004)

Factors	Unadjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value	Adjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value
Age, year				
≤30	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
31–50	0.49 (-0.24 to 1.22)	0.188	0.98 (0.42 to 1.54)	0.001
≥51	5.39 (3.99 to 6.79)	<0.001	3.03 (1.80 to 4.26)	<0.001
Sexual identity				
Female	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Male	1.09 (0.38 to 1.81)	0.003	1.03 (0.54 to 1.52)	<0.001
Others	-1.49 (-3.26 to 0.28)	0.099	0.13 (-0.91 to 1.18)	0.803
Marital status				
Single	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Married/domestic partnership	3.10 (2.16 to 4.04)	<0.001	0.98 (0.27 to 1.69)	0.007
Divorced/widowed/ separated	3.83 (1.91 to 5.75)	<0.001	1.01 (-0.50 to 2.52)	0.189
Education level				
Illiterate/primary school/ junior high school	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Senior high school/diploma/ high vocational	-0.98 (-3.26 to 1.30)	0.398	...	...
Bachelor's degree/ higher education	-0.11 (-2.40 to 2.17)	0.924	...	...
Occupation				
Unemployed/retried	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Employed	0.16 (-1.05 to 1.36)	0.799	...	...
College student	-0.45 (-1.66 to 0.76)	0.466	...	...
Religion				
Irreligion	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Buddhist	2.45 (1.46 to 3.44)	<0.001	1.19 (0.54 to 1.83)	<0.001
Christian/Muslim/Others	2.06 (0.36 to 3.76)	0.018	0.92 (-0.19 to 2.02)	0.104

[†]The effect estimates are presented weighted.

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale.

Table S2 Linear Regression Model Results of Factors Associated with COVID-19-Related Public Stigma (n=4,004) (Continued)

Factors	Unadjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value	Adjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value
Region of residence				
Capital city and its environs	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Non-capital city and its environs	1.02 (0.46 to 1.59)	<0.001	0.40 (0.03 to 0.77)	0.035
Living status				
Alone	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
With family	1.10 (0.20 to 1.99)	0.017	...	...
With others	-0.69 (-2.12 to 0.73)	0.340	...	...
Person income, baht/month				
≤10,000	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
10,001 – 20,000	-0.51 (-1.32 to 0.30)	0.214	...	...
>20,000	1.11 (0.34 to 1.87)	0.005	...	...
Reimbursement scheme				
Government/state enterprises	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Universal coverage scheme	-1.82 (-2.88 to -0.75)	0.001	...	...
Social security scheme	-1.40 (-2.49 to -0.31)	0.012	...	...
Self-payment/others	-1.71 (-2.77 to -0.64)	0.002	...	...
History of mental illness				
No	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Yes	-0.83 (-1.97 to 0.30)	0.150	...	...
History of chronic NCDs [‡]				
No	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Yes	2.28 (1.34 to 3.23)	<0.001	...	...

[†]The effect estimates are presented weighted.

[‡]To includes diabetes mellitus, hypertension, dyslipidemia, stroke and heart disease, chronic kidney disease, chronic lung disease, and cancer.

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale; NCD, non-communicable diseases.

Table S2 Linear Regression Model Results of Factors Associated with COVID-19-Related Public Stigma (n=4,004) (Continued)

Factors	Unadjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value	Adjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value
Income loss during the COVID-19 pandemic				
No	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Yes	0.28 (-0.40 to 0.95)	0.418	...	...
Financial problems during the COVID-19 pandemic				
No	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Yes	0.53 (-0.12 to 1.17)	0.111	...	...
Information exposure during the COVID-19 pandemic				
<1 hour/day	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
1–2 hours/day	0.54 (-0.17 to 1.25)	0.136	...	...
≥3 hours/day	1.33 (0.41 to 2.26)	0.005	...	...
Confirmed cases in the community				
No	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Yes	0.45 (-0.36 to 1.26)	0.280	...	...
Not known	-0.47 (-1.25 to 0.32)	0.244	...	...
Quarantine status				
Never	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Past	0.74 (0.02 to 1.46)	0.043	0.79 (0.32 to 1.27)	0.001
Current	0.56 (-0.35 to 1.48)	0.228	0.64 (0.01 to 1.27)	0.046
Working from home				
No	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Yes	-0.17 (-0.98 to 0.65)	0.688	...	...
Perceived social support				
Low perceived support	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Moderate perceived support	0.97 (-0.34 to 2.29)	0.147	...	...
High perceived support	1.92 (0.61 to 3.22)	0.004	...	...

[†]The effect estimates are presented weighted.

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale.

Table S2 Linear Regression Model Results of Factors Associated with COVID-19-Related Public Stigma (n=4,004) (Continued)

Factors	Unadjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value	Adjusted beta coefficient (95% CI)[†]	P value
Resilient coping				
Low resilient copers	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Medium resilient copers	-1.01 (-2.03 to 0.01)	0.052	-0.76 (-1.46 to -0.05)	0.036
High resilient copers	-1.00 (-1.97 to -0.03)	0.043	-0.82 (-1.51 to -0.14)	0.019
Fear of COVID-19				
No/minimal	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Moderate	5.01 (4.23 to 5.79)	<0.001	2.06 (1.35 to 2.76)	<0.001
Severe	12.76 (11.94 to 13.57)	<0.001	5.11 (4.30 to 5.92)	<0.001
Perceived risk of COVID-19 infection				
Low perceived risk	Reference (1.00)		Reference (1.00)	
Medium perceived risk	6.95 (6.43 to 7.47)	<0.001	5.60 (5.05 to 6.15)	<0.001
High perceived risk	15.11 (14.46 to 15.76)	<0.001	12.21 (11.47 to 12.96)	<0.001

[†]The effect estimates are presented weighted.

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; COVID-19, coronavirus disease-2019; COVID-PSS, coronavirus disease-2019 Public Stigma Scale.